

Variety	Maturity ^b <i>N. lugens</i> biotype ^c			Reaction to													
	<i>Nephotettix</i>																
	1	2	3	<i>N. virescens</i>	<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. mala-yanus</i>	<i>S. furcifera</i>	<i>R. dor-salis</i>	<i>S. incertulasa</i>	<i>C. suppressalis</i>	<i>C. mediana</i>	<i>M. pal-nalis</i>	<i>N. depunctalis</i>	<i>H. philippina</i>	<i>S. bipiformis</i>	<i>S. latiuscula</i>	<i>L. oratorius</i>
IR5	S	S	S	MR	MR	-	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR8	S	S	S	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR20	S	S	S	MR ^g	MR	R	S	MR	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR22	S	S	S	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR24	S	S	S	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR26	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	MR	S
IR28	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR29	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR30	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR32	R	R	R	MR ^h	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR34	R	R	R	R	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR36	R	R	R	MR ^h	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR38	R	R	R	MR ^h	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR40	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR42	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR43	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR44	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR45	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR46	R	R	R	MR ^d	MR	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR48	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR50	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR52	R	R	R	MR ^h	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR54	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR56	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR58	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR60	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	MR	S	S
IR62	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	MR	S	S

^aBased on replicated experiments. ^bDAS = days after seeding. ^cBased on greenhouse evaluation of seedlings. ^dBased on a screenhouse evaluation of 40- to 70-d-old plants. ^eBased on the reaction of 30- and 11-d-old plants in the greenhouse. ^fBased on field observations at 30 d after transplanting. Varieties with ratings as based on the standard evaluation system of 1-3 are considered resistant (R), 5-7 moderately resistant (MR), and 9 susceptible (S). ^gOccasional susceptible reactions. Least resistant of the IR varieties except IR22, which is highly susceptible. ^hReaction to biotype varies, occasionally being susceptible and often resistant. IR46 has field resistance to biotype 2. Tests still to be conducted.

Green leafhopper (GLH) virulence on three rices

H. R. Rapusas and E. A. Heinrichs,
Entomology Department, IRRRI

Varieties resistant to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) are widely grown in Asia. We studied the extent of selection after rearing GLH on a resistant variety for six generations and determined its virulence on another variety with the same major gene for resistance.

GLH colonies were reared separately in the greenhouse on Ptb 8 and IR42 for 6 generations and on TN1 for more than 50 generations. Colony virulence was evaluated based on population growth on Ptb 8, IR42, and TN1. Ptb 8 and IR42 have the *glh 4* gene for resistance to *N. virescens*.

Thirty-day-old potted plants of the test varieties were covered with 10- × 90-cm mylar film cages and arranged in a randomized complete block design with 10 replications on a water pan tray in the greenhouse. The plants in each cage were infested with 5 pair (male and female) of 3-d-old GLH adults and their progeny were counted 25 d later.

Significantly more progeny per female were produced by the Ptb 8 colony on Ptb 8 than on the IR42 and TN1 colonies (see table). The progeny produced by the IR42 colony also was highest on IR42, although it did not differ significantly from that produced on the Ptb 8 colony. The TN1 colony had the lowest population growth on the three varieties.

Results indicate that the *N. virescens* colonies were most virulent on the variety on which the colony was reared,

Population growth (progeny/female) of *N. virescens* colonies on three rice varieties.

Colony	Progeny/female ^a		
	Ptb 8	IR42	TN1
Ptb 8	75 a (b)	30 ab (c)	116 a (a)
IR42	13b (c)	43 a (b)	79 b (a)
TN1	22b (b)	19 b (b)	65 b (a)

^aSeparation of means in a column or in a row (in parentheses) by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

indicating a certain degree of GLH adaptation to the variety. Although Ptb

8 and IR42 have the same major gene for GLH resistance, the rate of

adaptation was faster on Ptb 8 than on IR42. *ℳ*

Reaction of rices to *Sogatella furcifera* in free-choice and no-choice seedling bulk tests

J. Singh, Plant Breeding Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India, and H. R. Rapusas and A. Romena, Entomology Department, IRRI

We evaluated the reactions of N22, ARC10239, ADR52, Podiwi A8, N'Diang Marie, and IR2035-117-3 to *S. furcifera* in the IRRI greenhouse in 1984. TN1 was the susceptible check.

In the free-choice test, seeds were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. One row of 25 seeds per entry was sown for each of 3 replications. Seven-day-old seedlings were infested with five 2d- and 3d-instar *S. furcifera* nymphs per seedling. Damage was rated at 8 d when susceptible TN1 died and 10 d when most varieties showed hopperburn.

Reaction of rice varieties to *S. furcifera* in free-choice and no-choice tests, IRRI, 1984.

Variety	Damage rating ^a		
	Free-choice test		No-choice test
	8	10	
N22	5 (0.00) b	7 (0.57) ab	4 (-0.28) bc
ARC10239	4 (-0.38) ab	6 (0.31) a	5 (-0.05) c
ADR52	3 (-0.57) ab	3 (-0.57) a	3 (-0.46) b
Podiwi A8	4 (-0.19) b	6 (0.50) ab	7 (0.45) d
N'Diang Marie	5 (0.00) b	6 (0.38) ab	4 (-0.17) bc
IR2035-117-3	2 (-0.88) a	4 (-0.19) a	1 (-1.38) a
TN1	9 (1.49) c	9 (1.49) b	9 (1.27) e

^a Test for paired values for no-choice and free-choice at P = 0.05 = nonsignificant. Figures in parentheses are transformed score values for ranked data.

Reaction was rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0 to 9 scale (see table).

In the no-choice test, 19-d-old potted plants were covered with a 10- × 90-cm mylar cage and arranged in randomized complete block design with 5 replications. Five pair of 3-d-old *S. furcifera*

adults were released per cage. Damage was rated 21 d later (see table).

IR2035-117-3 was most resistant in both tests. At 10 d after infestation in the free-choice test, ADR52 performed as well as IR2035-117-3. TN1 was most susceptible, followed by Podiwi A8 and N22. *ℳ*

Response of resistant rices to brown planthoppers (BPH) collected in Mindanao, Philippines

F. G. Medrano and E. A. Heinrichs, Entomology Department, IRRI

IR36 and IR42 (with *bph 2* gene for resistance to BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*) have been extensively grown in the Philippines, Indonesia, and Vietnam for about 7 yr. In 1982, they were attacked by BPH in Mindanao, Philippines. A BPH population was collected in Mindanao and evaluated at IRRI using the standard seedbox screening, population growth development, and growth index studies. IR26 with *Bph 1*, IR36 and IR42 with *bph 2*, and Rathu Heenati and IR56 with *Bph 3* were screened for resistance.

In the population development study, 10 newly hatched nymphs were caged on 35-d-old potted test varieties. The number of BPH/cage was recorded 40 d

1. Resistance of selected varieties to Mindanao BPH, 1983.

2. Resistance of selected varieties to Mindanao BPH, 1984. M-36, M-25, and M-42 = Mindanao BPH reared on IR36, IR26, and IR42, respectively.